

A study of renal hilar structure and its clinical significance**Diana Laishram¹, Deepti Shastri²**¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences & Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata.²Professor, Department of Anatomy, Vinayaka Mission's Kirupananda Variyar Medical College, Salem, Tamil Nadu

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Advancement in minimally invasive nephron sparing surgeries require a precise knowledge of the normal and variant anatomy of vascular structures at the hilum of the kidney. But the study in the variations in arrangement of structures at the renal hilum has not gained much interest up till now compared to literature available on the intra-renal vascular pattern of the kidneys.**Aims and Objective:** So, the study was conducted to observe the arrangements of the renal hilar structures from anterior to posterior and from above downwards just before entering into the hilum.**Materials and Methods:** 100 embalmed cadaveric kidneys (44 left kidneys; 56 right kidneys) with intact renal hilar structures were studied for a period of 6 years. Grossly damaged kidneys were excluded for the study. The arrangement of the structures in the hilar region were noted and classified into various patterns.**Results:** In 75% of the cases the anterior division of renal artery is the uppermost structure in the hilum. The classical pattern of renal hilar structure arrangement from anterior to posterior as renal vein, renal artery & renal pelvis was observed in 65%. A high incidence (4.167%) of renal arterial variations in comparison to 2.083% incidence of variations of renal veins were observed.**Conclusion:** Renal hilar structures variations are useful for operating surgeons to identify and individually to clamp the hilar structures. This is advantageous over en-bloc clamping. Branching pattern of the renal artery is very important in analysing radiographic interpretation of renal vasculature for planning surgical procedures.**Keywords:** Hilum, Renal Artery, Renal Pelvis, Renal Vein.

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Introduction

Kidneys are a pair of excretory organs situated one on each side of the vertebral column retroperitoneally. Each kidney is bean shaped and presents thick and rounded superior pole and thin and pointed inferior pole. Superiorly, they are at level with the upper border of the twelfth thoracic vertebra, and inferiorly, with the third lumbar vertebra. Renal hilum is a deep vertical fissure situated in its medial border which lies about 5 cm from the midline opposite the lower border of L1 vertebra. It is bounded by anterior and posterior lips and contains the renal vessels and nerves and the renal pelvis. The positions of the renal hilar structures are the renal vein (anterior), renal artery (intermediate) and the pelvis (posterior). Usually, an arterial branch from the main renal artery runs over the superior margin of the renal pelvis to enter the hilum on the posterior aspect of the pelvis, and a renal venous tributary often leaves the hilum in the same plane. Above the hilum, the medial border is related to the suprarenal gland and below to the origin of the ureter. It communicates with the renal sinus within the

kidney [1]. According to conventional description in standard anatomy textbooks, at the hilum, usually the renal vein is the anterior most with the renal artery posterior to it and the pelvis of kidney lying further posteriorly [2]. Near the hilum, each renal artery divides into an anterior and posterior, and these divides into segmental arteries supplying the renal vascular segments. Accessory renal arteries are common (30% of the individuals) arising from the aorta above or below the main renal artery and follow it to the hilum. They are regarded as persistent embryonic lateral splanchnic arteries. Accessory vessels to the inferior pole cross anterior to the ureter and causes hydronephrosis by obstructing the ureter. In children with pelvi-ureteric junction obstruction, a crossing vessel is found in 28% cases. Posterior division of renal artery and posterior tributary of renal vein might be seen entering posterior to pelvis in some cases [3,4]. The large renal vein lies anterior to the renal arteries and open into the inferior vena cava almost at right angles. The left renal vein may be double, one vein passing posteri-

or and the other anterior, to the aorta before joining the inferior vena cava referred to as persistence of 'renal collar'. The anterior renal vein may be absent so that there is a single retro-aortic left renal vein. Knowledge of the variations of renal vascular anatomy is important in the exploration and treatment of renal trauma, renal transplantation, renovascular hypertension, renal artery embolization, angioplasty or vascular reconstruction for congenital and acquired lesions, surgery for abdominal aortic aneurysm and conservative or radical renal surgery [5,6,7]. Laparoscopic partial nephrectomy (LPN) has demonstrated benefits compared to open partial nephrectomy [8]. LPN is technically challenging because of limited field of vision and the need for hilar dissection for vascular clamping [9]. Clamping of individual structures at the hilum is preferred rather than en-bloc clamping [10]. Knowledge of structures at the renal hilum is thus necessary prior to any surgical intervention of the kidney.

Aim and Objective

To study the arrangement of the renal hilar structures from anterior to posterior and from above downwards and its clinical significances.

Materials and Methods

The study was carried out in 100 embalmed cadaveric kidneys (44 left kidneys and 56 right kidneys) for a period of 6 years in the Department of Anatomy of both VMKVMC, Salem & JIMSH, Budge

Budge. Only kidneys with intact renal hilar structures were included. Grossly damaged kidney was excluded for the study. The division patterns of the renal vessels, their arrangements just before their entry into the hilum & their correlation with the renal pelvis were observed. The arrangements of the structures from anterior to posterior and from above downwards were noted & classified into various patterns. The kidneys with variation in the hilum structures were compared with the findings of other authors and are statistically analyzed for its relevance.

The abbreviations used in this study were: V- Renal Vein A - Renal Artery P - Renal Pelvis AD - Anterior Division of Renal Artery PD - Posterior Division of Renal Artery AT - Anterior Tributary of Renal Vein, PT - Posterior Tributary of Renal Vein.

Observations and Results

The arrangement of renal artery, renal vein & pelvis from above downwards shows great variations in their relation at the hilum. In 75% of the cases the anterior division of renal artery is the uppermost structure present at the hilum. Out of 100 kidneys studied, we observed the classical pattern of renal hilar structure arrangement from anterior to posterior as renal vein, renal artery & renal pelvis in 65%. Different patterns of arrangement of hilum structures from anterior to posterior other than VAN was observed more on the left side than right side.

Table 1: Shows arrangement of structure at the hilum from above downwards (n=100).

Pattern	Arrangement of structure at the hilum (above downwards)	Percentage (%)	Figure
1	V-A-P	10%	Fig-1
2	AD-V-PD-P	50%	Fig-2
3	A-V-P	15%	Fig-3
4	AD-AT-P-PD-PT	5%	Fig-4
5	AD-AT-PD-V-PT	10%	Fig-5
6	AT-A-PT-P	5%	Fig-6
7	P-A-V	5%	Fig-7

Table 2: Shows arrangement of structure at the hilum from anterior to posterior (n=100).

Pattern	Arrangement of structure at the hilum (anterior to posterior)	Percentage (%)	Figure
1	V-A-P	65%	Fig-1
2	AD-V-PD-P	15%	Fig-8
3	A-V-P	15%	Fig-9
4	V-AD-PD-P	5%	Fig-10

Discussions

A high degree of variations is exhibited by renal vessels especially arteries [11] Present study also showed high incidence (4.167%) of renal arterial variations in comparison to 2.083% incidence of variations of renal veins. Various studies had been carried out on renal vessels till date. Raghu Jetty [12] and Vaghela et al. [13] studied the length of renal vein and thus differed from our study as this

parameter was not taken into account in the present study.

Variation of renal veins is found to be more on the right side than left [14]. The incidence of an additional renal vein is reported to be 3.3% on the right side and 2.6% on the left side [15]. Supernumerary renal arteries had been reported in 32.25% of kidneys [16].

There has been report of additional renal artery in 2.4% of cadavers on the right side and 1.8% on the left side in 190 cadavers [17]. Satyapal et al. reported additional renal arteries on right side in 18.6% and in 27.6% cases on left side in his study of 1244 pairs of kidneys [18]. Edman stated additional arteries incidence in the range of 8.7% to 75.7% which can cause obstruction leading to hydronephrosis [19]. Additional renal arteries incidence was not observed in our study. The renal vessels and ureter relationship was preserved in all the specimens in our study.

Many researchers studied the renal vessels at perihilar and hilar region but there are very few reports about the arrangement of renal hilar structures. We classified the arrangement of renal hilar structures from above to downward into 7 patterns and arrangement of hilar structures from anterior to posterior into 4 patterns. The normal anatomy of arrangement of renal hilar structures is described in FIG-1 while rest of the pattern described the variation in disposition of renal hilar structures. The results of our study were compared with similar previous studies which were done on the patterns of the hilar structures as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of arrangement pattern of renal structures in the hilum with other previous studies.

Pattern in Percentage (%)	Arrangement of structure at the hilum (anterior to posterior)	Present study	Pereira-Correia JA et al. [20]	Trivedi et al. [21]	Kumar N et al. [22]	Jadhav S. et. al [23]
1	V-A-P	65%	83%	19%	45.8%	22.8%
2	AD-V-PD-P	15%	-	23%	2.10%	5.26%
3	A-V-P	15%	3%	-	28.10%	-
4	V-AD-PD-P	5%	-	8%	-	9.64%

[Figure 1: From above downwards VAP; Figure 2: From above downwards AD-V-PD-P; Figure 3: From above downwards A-V-P; Figure 4 – From above downwards AD-AT-P-PD-PT]

[Figure 5: From above downwards AD-AT-PD-V-PT; Figure 6: From above downwards AT-A-PT-P; Figure 7: From above downwards P-A-V; Figure 8 – From above downwards AD-V-PD-P]

[Figure 9: From above downwards A-V-P; Figure 10: From above downwards V-AD-PD-P]

It is noted that, each study shows variable number of patterns and incidence which may be because of anatomic variations of renal vessels which are common in general population with different frequencies among several ethnic and racial groups. Present study observed that variant patterns are more common on left side which is in favor of other studies [21-23]. Embryologically, the right renal vein develops from a single anastomotic channel whereas the left renal vein develops from multiple anastomotic channels. Hence the predominant left sided occurrence may have an embryological explanation. Developmental malformations may change the interrelationship of the hilar structures.

The present study has demonstrated that in majority of cases branches and tributaries of renal vessels occupy the prehilum and hilar region rather than the main trunks of renal vessels. This observation is supported by various studies conducted by Sampaio et al. [5] on vascular relationship of ureteropelvic junction which concluded that in the majority of cases a branch of renal artery and/or venous tributaries lies in close proximity of the pelvis implying pre-hilar branching of renal artery.

A different variant pattern of disposition of renal hilar structures makes the crowding of structures at renal hilum and it may confuse surgeon and pose difficulty during surgical dissection at hilar region and it may produce iatrogenic trauma to these structures and create emergency during surgery especially during laparoscopic partial nephrectomy. Therefore, it is essential to have a detailed knowledge of renal hilar structures. Surgical interventions that require hilar dissections are technically more challenging in laparoscopic approach as compared to open surgeries [24, 25]. For many operations on the kidney including Nephron sparing surgeries like partial nephrectomy by laparoscope is treatment of choice and in this surgery hilar dissection is one of the important steps. In cases of renal hilar tumors laparoscopic partial ne-

phrectomy is being done with a limited field of vision.

Conclusion

Knowledge of renal hilar structures variations is useful for operating surgeons to identify and individually clamp the hilar structures, which is advantageous over en-bloc clamping. Knowledge of branching pattern of the renal artery is very important for the proper analysis of radiographic interpretation of renal vasculature and for planning surgical procedures in cases of renal trauma, renal transplantation, and partial nephrectomy. The variations in the branching patterns of the renal vessels are critical issues and a challenging task for a radiologist who interpret renal angiograms and for the urologists who perform laparoscopies.

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